

Kinetics of Ce(IV) Oxidation of 3-Bromo Propionic Acid in Aqueous Nitric Acid Solutions

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Kinetics of oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid by ceric ammonium nitrate in aqueous nitric acid solutions have been reported. A first order dependence in each cerium(IV) and 3-bromo propionic acid has been observed. Ionic strength of the medium showed positive effect on the reaction rate while nitrate ions are found to have retarding effect. Unlike other Ce(IV) oxidation processes in nitric acid solutions no effect of hydrogen ions was observed. A plausible mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed. Various Arrhenius parameters have been computed.

THE study of oxidation mechanism of acids has been an interesting problem since long. Kinetic investigations regarding the oxidative processes involving organic acids and Ce(IV) have been reported by many workers¹⁻¹⁰. The literature on the study of kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid by Ce(IV) is scanty. The present study mainly aims at getting more information about Ce(IV) oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid in presence of higher concentrations of nitric acid. The results were used to characterise the active oxidising species of cerium(IV) in aqueous solutions of nitric acid and finally a suitable reaction mechanism was proposed.

Materials and Methods

3-Bromo propionic acid (Fluka) AG was used as such in all kinetic investigations. Ceric ammonium nitrate, ceric sulphate, nitric acid and ferrous ammonium sulphate were all (B.D.H.) A.R. grade samples. Other chemicals were either (B.D.H.) or (Riedel) grade.

A stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by usual method and ceric ammonium nitrate solution was prepared by direct weighing and standardised against the standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator.

The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the amounts of remaining Ce(IV) at different intervals of time. The requisite volumes of standard solutions of ceric ammonium nitrate, nitric acid and water were taken in 100 ml conical flask (coated from outside with black Japan), kept in a thermostat maintained at desired temperature. To this was added requisite volume of 3-bromo propionic acid solution which too was maintained at

the temperature of the reaction. The kinetics of the reaction were followed by removing 5 ml aliquots from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and adding it to a known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution, the excess of which was estimated with standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as redox indicator. Reproducible results were always obtained.

Results and Discussion

Order of reaction with respect to cerium(IV): In order to investigate the dependence of the reaction on Ce(IV), the reactions were studied at different concentrations of ceric ammonium nitrate by isolation method. Ce(IV)-(3-bromo propionic acid) reaction was quite fast in the beginning of the reaction, therefore the value of k , i.e., first order rate constant has been determined from the slope (measured in the beginning of the reaction) of the graph plotted between time and concentration of Ce(IV) in all sets of experiments. The slope gives the value of $(-dc/dt)$ in terms of ml of Ce(IV) consumed per minute. The value of k_1 was calculated by dividing the value of $(-dc/dt)$ in terms of gm mole/min by the concentration of Ce(IV) at which $(-dc/dt)$ is measured. Table 1 contains the results of various experiments at different concentrations of Ce(IV). The 3rd column of Table 1 shows the concentration of Ce(IV) at which $(-dc/dt)$ was measured. A close examination of results of Table 1 indicates that the values of k_1 do not vary significantly with the change in concentration of Ce(IV) and are thus practically constant. The average value of k_1 is $5.66 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with 0.34% average deviation. Thus the reaction follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV).

Order of reaction with respect to 3-bromo propionic acid: In order to find out the order of the reaction with respect to the reductant, the reactions were studied at different concentrations of 3-bromo

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TABLE 1

Temperature 30°
[3-Bromopropionic acid] = $1.14 \times 10^{-2} M$
[HNO₃] = 2.0N

[Ceric ammonium nitrate] × 10 ² N	$A \frac{dc}{dt} \times 10^6$ gm. mole min ⁻¹	[Ce(IV)]	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
0.60	2.025	0.37×10^{-3}	5.57
0.80	3.509	0.59×10^{-3}	5.81
1.25	6.540	1.12×10^{-3}	5.83
1.60	8.435	1.30×10^{-3}	6.37
2.00	8.754	16.40×10^{-4}	5.33
2.50	10.940	21.90×10^{-4}	5.06

propionic acid and at fixed concentrations of other reactants. In this case, also the values of k_1 were determined from the slopes at fixed concentration of Ce(IV) for different concentrations of 3-bromo propionic acid with time. The results are recorded in Table 2 which shows that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the concentration of the reductant and the values of k_2 (second order rate constant) obtained on dividing k_1 values by concentrations of 3-bromo propionic acid are practically constant, which shows first order dependence of the reaction on 3-bromo propionic acid. Thus total order of the reaction is two, unity being with respect to each Ce(IV) and 3-bromo propionic acid. The average k_2 value at 30° is $5.14 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with average deviation of $\approx 0.11\%$.

TABLE 2

Temperature 30°

[Ceric ammonium nitrate] = $1.00 \times 10^{-2} N$
[HNO₃] = 2.00N

[3-Bromo propionic acid] × 10 ² M	$\left(-\frac{dc}{dt}\right) \times 10^6$ gm. mole min ⁻¹	[Ce(IV)]* × 10 ²	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	k_2 l.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0.57	1.964	7.02	2.80	4.93
0.80	2.806	7.02	3.99	5.00
1.00	3.650	7.02	5.20	5.20
1.14	4.356	7.26	5.99	5.28
1.60	6.098	7.26	8.39	5.24
2.00	7.551	7.26	10.38	5.19

Ce(IV)* = Concentration of Ce(IV) at which $(-dc/dt)$ values were determined.

Effects of ionic strength, hydrogen and nitrate ions : The results of various experiments at different ionic strengths of the medium indicate that the value of k_1 increases on increasing the ionic strength of the medium. The ionic strength of the medium was changed by addition of a requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. The increase in reaction rate due to ionic strength of the medium seems to be difficult to be explained under the conditions of experiments

shown in Table 3. However, in view of the positive effect of ionic strength, it was thought essential to maintain ionic strength of the medium constant in order to investigate the effect of hydrogen and nitrate ions on reaction rate. The effect of hydrogen ions was first studied by varying concentrations of nitric acid and the results are included in Table 3, which indicates that six-fold increase in nitric acid concentration brings about 80% retardation in the reaction velocity. This retardation in velocity is due to the combined effect of nitrate and hydrogen ions which increase on increasing the concentrations of nitric acid. In order to single out the effect of hydrogen ion, the reaction was studied at different concentrations of perchloric acid at constant ionic strength and at fixed concentration of nitrate ions and the results are recorded in Table 3 which shows that reaction velocity is independent of hydrogen ions concentration. The neutral influence of hydrogen ions on reaction velocity and the results at different concentrations of nitric acid clearly indicate the retarding effect of nitrate ions. The retardation in reaction velocity due to nitrate ions may be ascribed due to conversion of Ce(OH)³⁺ into much less reactive species by complexation with nitrate ions as shown below :

Such behaviour has also been noted by previous workers¹¹⁻¹³. The neutral effect of perchloric acid is solely due to hydrogen ions as perchlorate ions do not form complex with Ce(IV) species and are known to have no effect on reaction velocity^{14,15}.

TABLE 3

[Ceric ammonium nitrate] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} N$
[3-Bromo propionic acid] = $1.14 \times 10^{-2} M$
Error = $\pm 0.5\%$ (unless otherwise mentioned).

Temp. in °C	[HNO ₃] N	Ionic strength (μ) M	[HClO ₄] M	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
30	2.0	2.012	—	5.99†
"	"	2.112	—	6.25
"	"	2.412	—	7.50
"	"	2.612	—	11.26
"	"	3.012	—	14.76
"	2.0	3.024	0.00	9.99†
"	"	"	0.10	9.77
"	"	"	0.20	10.03
"	"	"	0.40	10.10
"	"	"	0.50	10.03
"	"	"	0.80	9.83†
"	"	"	1.00	9.91
"	0.5	3.024	—	10.01*
"	1.5	"	—	7.85*
"	2.0	"	—	5.28*
"	2.5	"	—	3.07*
"	3.0	"	—	2.00*
35*	2.0	2.012	—	4.14
40*	"	"	—	7.49
45*	"	"	—	11.26

* Where [3-Bromo propionic acid] = $0.57 \times 10^{-2} M$

† error = 0.5%.

Temperature effect: Ce(IV) oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid was found to be markedly affected due to rise in temperature in the temperature range of 30° to 45°. The results are given in Table 3. The values of activation parameters were determined from the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$. The values of energy of activation (ΔE), entropy of activation (ΔS), free energy (ΔF) and frequency factor (A) come out to be 17.16 K.cal/mole, -8.965 e.u., 19.94 K.cal/mole and 19.35×10^{10} l.mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ respectively.

Stoichiometric studies showed that four equivalents of Ce(IV) are consumed per mole oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid. Formic acid and bromo acetic acid were tested and identified as reaction products.

A close examination of Ce(IV) oxidation of 3-bromo propionic acid in aqueous nitric acid leads us to decide the reactive species of Ce(IV) in nitric acid solution only on careful perusal of effects of hydrogen and nitrate ions on reaction rate. Our kinetic data suggest us to assume that Ce(OH)³⁺ is the most predominant oxidising species. The reaction mechanism thus can be shown as given below :

The above reaction mechanism leads to a rate expression as

$$\text{rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{Ceric}][\begin{array}{c} \text{Br} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH} \end{array}] \quad (4)$$

When concentration of 3-bromo propionic acid is sufficiently large as compared to that of ceric then

$$\text{rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{Ceric}] \quad \dots (5)$$

where $k_1 = k_2[\text{Br-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}]$.

Thus the rate expression (4) is well in agreement with our experimental data and fully explains that Ce(IV)-(3-bromo propionic acid) reaction

- (I) follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV).
- (II) shows first order dependence on 3-bromo propionic acid, and
- (III) remains unaffected by an increase in hydrogen ions concentration.

References

1. N. H. FURMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 755.
2. H. H. WILLARD and P. YOUNG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 1322.
3. H. H. WILLARD and P. YOUNG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 132.
4. A. BENRATH and K. RULAND, *J. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 114, 267.
5. V. H. DODSON and A. H. BLACK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 3657.
6. S. D. ROSS and C. G. SWAIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1325.
7. K. K. SENGUPTA and S. ADITYA, *Z. physik. Chem.* (Frankfurt), 1963, 38, 125.
8. R. L. YADAV and B. V. BHAGWAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 389.
9. B. KRISHNA and K. C. TEWARI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.
10. R. N. MEHROTRA and S. GHOSH, *Z. physik. chem.* (Leipzig), 1962, 224, 57.
11. F. R. DUKE and A. A. FORIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2790.
12. A. W. WYLLIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1474.
13. J. SHORTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1868.
14. T. J. HARDWICK and E. ROBERTSON, *Oan. J. Chem.*, 1951, 29, 818.
15. E. G. JONES and F. G. SOPER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 802.